

AN ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF VIRTAKO (INSECTICIDE) IN SHAHJAHANPUR DISTRICT OF UTTAR PRADESH

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Abstract:

The Present study entitled "Study on marketing of insecticide virtako in Shahjahanpur District Oo Uttar Pradesh". It has been founded that there are three marketing channel involved in marketing of Virtako insecticide in Shahjahanpur District of Uttar Pradesh, (Channel 1- Producer- Wholesaler-Consumer), (Channel 2- Producer- Wholesaler-Consumer), (Channel 3- Producer- Retailer- Consumer). The channel 2 is preferred majorly by the respondents in marketing of Virtako insecticide in the study area. In channel 1 the total marketing cost is Rs 85, total marketing margin is Rs 250 and the marketing efficiency of channel 1 is 4.58%. In channel 2 the total marketing cost is Rs. 125 total marketing margin is Rs. 350 and the marketing efficiency of channel 2 is 3.42%. In channel 3 the total marketing cost is Rs 95, total marketing margin is Rs 280 and the marketing efficiency of channel 3 is 4.06%.

Keyword: Marketing Margin, Marketing Efficiency, Marketing Cost, Market Share.

Introduction

Insecticides are chemicals used to control or eliminate insect pests. They are commonly used in agriculture, horticulture, and in homes and gardens to protect crops and plants from damage caused by insects. Insecticides work by either killing the insects outright or by interfering with their ability to reproduce or feed. They can be applied to crops as sprays or dusts, or to the soil as granules or liquid formulations. While insecticides can be effective in controlling insect pests, they can also have negative impacts on the environment and human health. Some insecticides can persist in the environment for long periods, and exposure to certain insecticides can lead to health problems for both humans and animals. Therefore, the use of insecticides is regulated and controlled to minimize their negative impacts. The dual mode of action present in Virtako ensures a long lasting protection from Stem Borer in Rice & Corn and Early Shoot borer in Sugarcane. Virtako helps in the growth of extra productive tillers & profuse root development along with a lush green healthy crop and gives an extra advantage of increase in the crop growth. Virtako does not stunt the plant growth and provides better ROI, higher yields and peace of mind to the growers.

Research Methodology:**Selection of the District:**

There are 75 District and 18 division in Uttar Pradesh State. Out of these Shahjahanpur district of Uttar Pradesh was selected for the present study on the basis of maximum area under sugarcane cultivation,

Selection of Block:

There are 15 block in the district. Out of these Jalalabad was selected purposively for the study.

Selection of Villages:**Results And Discussion****Table 1: Market margin, market share and Market efficiency of Virtako Channel I****Producer – Wholesaler- Consumer**

S. No	Particulars	Price/5Kg
1	Net price received by producer	1150
2	Cost incurred by the producer	
a	Packing cost	20
b	Packing material cost	10
c	Miscellaneous charges	20
3	Total marketing cost	50
4	Sale price of producer/Purchase price of Wholesaler	1250
	Cost incurred by the Wholesaler	
	Loading and unloading Charges	5
	Carriage up to shop	15
	Miscellaneous charges	15

A complete list of all villages of Jalalabad block was obtained from the block development office. Thereafter these villages was arranged in ascending order on the basis of area of sugarcane cultivation . Thus, out of total villages 5% villages was selected randomly for the present study.

Selection of Respondents:

From the selected village, list of all the sugarcane cultivator was obtained from the block development office in each selected village. Ascending order on the basis of size of their land holding for the selection of cultivators from families was listed and 10% farmers from each village were randomly selected and then the selected farmers were classified into five sizes of groups.

Analytical Tools**Mean**

$$m = \frac{\text{sum of the terms}}{\text{number of terms}}$$

Marketing Efficiency

$$\frac{\text{Consumer paid price}}{\text{Total marketing cost} + \text{Total marketing margin}}$$

Total marketing cost + Total marketing margin

Marketing Cost:

$$\text{Marketing Cost (MC)} = \frac{\Delta TC}{\Delta Q}$$

Marketing Margin –

Product price- Raw Material

Market Share-

$$\text{Market share} = \left(\frac{\text{Total sales of the company}}{\text{total sales of the market}} \right) \times 100$$

	Marketing cost	35
	Margin of Retailer	250
	Sale price of retailer/ Purchase price of consumer	1535
	Price spread	385
	Marketing efficiency	4.58%
	Producer's share in consumer rupee	74.91%

Table 1: In channel 1 the net price received by producer is Rs 1150, the marketing cost incurred by producer in marketing of Virtako (Insecticide) is Rs 50. The Sale price of Virtako (Insecticide) from producer to wholesaler is Rs. 1250. The marketing cost incurred by wholesaler in marketing of Virtako (Insecticide) is Rs 35, the profit

margin of Virtako (Insecticide) is Rs 250. The sale price from wholesaler to consumer is Rs. 1535. The total marketing cost incurred in channel 1 is Rs. 85, the total marketing margin in channel is Rs. 250, the marketing efficiency of channel 1 is 4.58%.

Table 2: Market margin, market share and Market efficiency of Virtako Channel II.
Producer- Wholesaler- Retailer- Consumer

S. No	Particulars	Price/5 kg
1	Net price received by producer	1150
2	Cost incurred by the producer	
	Packing cost	10
	Packing material cost	10
	Transportation cost	20
	Loading and unloading charges	5
	Miscellaneous charges	20
	Marketing cost	65
	Sale price of producer/Purchase price of Commission agent	1215
3	Cost incurred by the Wholesaler	
	Loading and Unloading charges	15
	Marketing cost	15
	Margin of Commission agent	150
	Sale price of commission agent/ purchase price of retailer	1380
4	Cost incurred by the Retailer	
	Loading and unloading Charges	10
	Carriage up to shop	15
	Miscellaneous charges	20
	Marketing cost	45
	Margin of retailer	200
	Sale price of retailer/ purchase price of consumer	1625
5	Total Marketing cost	125
6	Net margin	350
7	Price Spread	475
	Marketing Efficiency	3.42%
8	Producer's share in consumer rupee	70.76%

Table 2: In channel 2 the net price received by producer is Rs 1150, the marketing cost incurred by producer in marketing of Virtako (Insecticide) is Rs 65. The sale price Virtako (Insecticide) from producer to wholesaler is Rs 1215. The marketing price incurred by wholesaler is Rs 15, the profit margin of wholesaler is Rs. 150. The selling price of Virtako (Insecticide) from wholesaler to retailer is Rs

1380. The marketing cost incurred by retailer in selling of Virtako (Insecticide) is Rs. 45 and the margin of retailer is Rs 200. The selling price of Virtako (Insecticide) from retailer to consumer is Rs 1625. In Channel 2, the total marketing cost incurred is Rs 125, the total marketing margin in channel 2 is Rs 350, the marketing efficiency of channel 2 is 3.42%.

Table 3: Market margin, market share and Market efficiency of Virtako Channel III
Producer- Retailer – Consumer

S. No	Particulars	Price/5 Kg
1	Net price received by producer	1150
2	Cost incurred by the producer	
	Packing cost	10
	Packing material cost	10
	Miscellaneous charges	20
	Total marketing cost	40
	Sale price of producer/Purchase price of Retailer	1190
3	Cost incurred by the Retailer	
	Loading and unloading Charges	20

	Carriage up to shop	15
	Miscellaneous charges	20
	Marketing cost	55
	Margin of Retailer	280
4	Sale price of retailer/ Purchase price of consumer	1525
5	Price spread	375
	Marketing Efficiency	4.06%
6	Producer's share in consumer rupee	75.40%

Table 3: In channel 3 the net price received by producer in marketing of Virtako (Insecticide) is Rs 1150, the marketing cost incurred by producer in marketing of Virtako (Insecticide) is Rs 40. The sale price of Virtako (Insecticide) from producer to retailer is Rs 1190. The marketing cost incurred by the retailer in marketing of Virtako (Insecticide) is Rs. 55, the profit margin of retailer is Rs 280. The selling price of Virtako (Insecticide) from retailer to consumer is Rs 1525. In Channel 3, the total marketing cost is Rs 95, the total marketing margin is Rs 280, the marketing efficiency of channel 3 is 4.06%.

Conclusion:

In the study it was found that there are three marketing channel which were involved in marketing of Virtako (Insecticide) in Shahjahanpur district of Uttar Pradesh is channel 1 (producer-wholealer-consumer), channel 2 (producer-wholesaler-retailer-consumer) and channel 3 (producer-retailer-consumer). The majorly preferred channel in marketing of Virtako (Insecticide) in Shahjahanpur district is channel 2 with majority of respondents response among the total selected sample in the study area. In channel 1 that total marketing cost is Rs 85, total marketing margin seen in channel 1 is Rs 250, marketing efficiency of channel 1 is 4.58%. In channel 2 that total marketing cost is Rs 125, total marketing margin seen in channel 2 is Rs. 350, marketing efficiency of channel 2 is 3.42%. In channel

3 that total marketing cost is Rs.95, total marketing margin seen in channel 2 is Rs. 280, marketing efficiency of channel 2 is 4.06%.

Reference

1. **Bhardwaj, T. and Sharma, J.P. (2013).** Impact of Pesticides Application in Agricultural Industry: An Indian Scenario, International Journal of Agriculture and Food Science Technology
2. **Gabbott, M. and Hogg, G. (1998).** Consumers and Services. pp 56-67. John Wiley and Sons, Chichester.
3. **Ghaswa, R., Tripaty, S. and Sharma, B. (2019).** Knowledge Adoption and Constraints of Soil Health card based Fertilizer Application in Rattam District, M.P., Indian Journal of Extension Education
4. **Sivakumar (1994).** Buying behaviour of farmers with reference to pesticides, Journal of Agricultural Marketing, 8.
5. **Stallworth, P. (2008).** Consumer behavior and marketing strategic, International Journal of Management and Communication Innovation, 2
6. **E Gummerson, (1998).** Market orientation applied to police service strategies, Vol 6, No,3
7. East R, (1997). The Role of Relationship Marketing Journal of Business Research, Vol 2, No 1